

Together,
there's
something
science
can do.

Issue Tracker 2026/02 February 19, 2026

[Researchers develop titanium dioxide-free tablet coating](#): On 19 January 2026, [Strozik et al. reported](#) in the *International Journal of Applied Pharmaceutics* the successful development of titanium dioxide-free film-coated drotaverine hydrochloride tablets using iron oxides as a substitute pigment. In a six-month stability study, the reformulated tablets remained stable and kept impurity levels within ICH Q3B(R2) limits, indicating that removing titanium dioxide did not compromise product quality. The study follows the [European Commission's 2022 ban on titanium dioxide](#) as a food additive in the EU and concerns that similar restrictions could extend to pharmaceutical excipients.

[FDA launches PreCheck pilot](#): On 3 February 2026, the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) opened applications for its voluntary PreCheck Pilot Program for newly built US drug manufacturing facilities. The expedited review pathway allows companies to receive early, facility-level feedback on plant design, quality systems and operational readiness before submitting a product application. The program prioritizes facilities that support critical medicine supply needs.

[Insilico Medicine and CMS announce AI-powered CNS and autoimmune collaboration](#): On 10 February 2026, Insilico Medicine and China Medical System Holdings Limited announced an agreement to jointly develop at least two new drug candidates for central nervous system (CNS) and autoimmune diseases. Insilico will use its AI platform to identify and design small-molecule drugs, while CMS will provide R&D funding of several tens of millions of Hong Kong dollars per program and lead clinical development, regulatory strategy, and commercialization.

[FDA accepts amended Moderna flu vaccine filing after refusal to file](#): On 18 February 2026, the US FDA agreed to review a revised application from Moderna for its seasonal influenza vaccine, just eight days [after issuing a controversial refusal to file letter](#). The agency objected to the design of Moderna's main clinical trial, which tested its vaccine against a standard-dose influenza shot rather than the higher dose vaccine typically recommended for adults aged 65 and older. After amending its filing to address these concerns, Moderna secured FDA review of the revised application, with a target decision date of 5 August 2026.